

Kinetics of Silver-Catalysed Oxidation of Formamide by Potassium Peroxydisulphate

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The kinetics of Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of formamide by peroxydisulphate ion in H_2SO_4 medium has been studied. The reaction is found to be first order w.r.t. $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, zero order w.r.t. formamide but specific rate is a function of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and formamide concentration. It decreases with an increase in $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ concentration but increases with an increase in formamide concentration. The specific rate is linearly related to $[\text{Ag}^+]$ by an expression $k = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} + 2.67 [\text{Ag}^+]$. Traces of allyl acetate inhibit the reaction appreciably. The energy of activation, frequency factor, free energy and entropy of activation respectively are 16.0 KCal/mole, $12.6 \times 10^6 \text{ sec}^{-1}$, 24.0 KCal/mole and -28.12 e.u. The mole ratio is found to be 1 mole of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ to 1 mole of formamide. The final products are CO_2 , NH_4^+ and H_2O . On the basis of these kinetic results, a possible reaction mechanism has been proposed and the corresponding rate expression deduced.

IN continuation of our study on the kinetics of oxidation of dimethyl formamide¹ by peroxydisulphate ion, the kinetics of oxidation of formamide was investigated, the results of which are presented in this paper. The only previous study of formamide oxidation by peroxydisulphate ion is by Mushran and coworkers² but the mechanism of oxidation of the organic substrate has not been worked out by them.

Experimental

The experimental technique followed was exactly similar to that adopted in dimethyl-formamide- $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ reaction¹. Formamide E.Merck G.R. was used after redistillation under reduced pressure and its standard solution was made by the saponification method due to Olsen³. Since the reaction mixture developed a white turbidity with time in aqueous medium, the kinetics was carried out in presence of 0.01N sulphuric acid.

Results

Just like dimethyl formamide reaction, the specific rate for formamide oxidation in each kinetic run was evaluated by subtracting the specific rate of self-decomposition of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, from that of the total reaction. The kinetic data obtained at varying concentrations of the reactants are represented graphically in Figs. 1 and 2 and the value of initial rate ($-\text{dc}/\text{dt}$), w.r.t. $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and w.r.t. formamide (reactant whose concentration is varied) and the specific rate evaluated therefrom are tabulated together in Table 1.

AgNO ₃ = 0.001M		H ₂ SO ₄ = 0.01M,		Temp. = 36°		
[K ₂ S ₂ O ₈] × 10 ² M	HCONH ₂ M	-dc/dt	k' × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	k'' × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	k × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	
0.5	0.1	1.90 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.77	1.53	5.24	
0.75	0.1	1.704 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.06	1.35	4.71	
1.0	0.1	2.173 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.00	1.21	3.79	
1.5	0.1	3.125 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.71	1.00	2.71	
2.0	0.1	4.00 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.19	0.92	2.27	
1.0	0.05	1.02 × 10 ⁻²	3.39	1.21	2.18	
1.0	0.1	1.219 × 10 ⁻²	5.00	1.21	3.79	
1.0	0.2	1.428 × 10 ⁻²	8.23	1.21	7.02	
1.0	0.3	1.562 × 10 ⁻²	9.60	1.21	8.39	
1.0	0.4	1.666 × 10 ⁻²	11.52	1.21	10.31	

k' and *k''* are the first order rate constant for the overall reaction for self decomposition of peroxydisulphate ion respectively and $k = k' - k''$.

The specific rate is seen to be a function of the initial concentration of both $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and HCONH_2 being governed by the expressions

$$-\log k = 2.13 + 28.5 [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] \quad \dots (i)$$

and

$$k = 1 \times 10^{-3} + 2.33 \times 10^{-2} [\text{HCONH}_2]_0 \quad \dots (ii)$$

The substitution of the above values of $-\text{dc}/\text{dt}$ in the Van Hoff differential equation gives the order of reaction w.r.t. $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and HCONH_2 as one and zero respectively.

Fig. 1. Effect of $K_2S_2O_8$ concentration
 $HCONH_2 = 0.1M$, $AgNO_3 = 0.001M$,
 $H_2SO_4 = 0.01M$, $Temp. = 35^\circ$.
 $K_2S_2O_8$: I— $0.005M$, II— $0.0075M$, III— $0.01M$,
 IV— $0.015M$, V— $0.02M$.

Fig. 2. Effect of $HCONH_2$ concentration
 $K_2S_2O_8 = 0.01M$, $AgNO_3 = 0.001M$,
 $H_2SO_4 = 0.01M$, $Temp. = 35^\circ$.
 $HCONH_2$: I— $0.05M$, II— $0.1M$, III— $0.2M$,
 IV— $0.3M$, V— $0.4M$.

Effect of Silver nitrate concentration

The specific rate is seen to be linearly related to the catalyst ($AgNO_3$) concentration, as shown by the data in Table 2 and the following relationship is seen to be followed :

$$k = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} + 2.67 C_{Ag^+} \quad \dots (iii)$$

TABLE 2

	$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.01M$, $H_2SO_4 = 0.01M$, Formamide = $0.1M$						$Temp. = 35^\circ$
$AgNO_3 \times 10^3 M$	0.25	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	
$k' \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	2.06	3.03	5.00	6.77	8.23	10.47	
$k'' \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	0.29	0.70	1.21	1.64	2.09	2.88	
$k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	1.77	2.33	3.79	5.13	6.14	7.59	
	$= k' - k''$.						

Effect of H_2SO_4 concentration

Since the kinetic runs have been carried out in presence of $0.01M$ sulphuric acid concentration in order to prevent the immediate hydrolysis of formamide, it was considered necessary to investigate the effect of variation of sulphuric acid concentration on the rate of reaction.

The kinetic results at four concentrations of sulphuric acid are reported in Table 3.

TABLE 3

	$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.01M$, $AgNO_3 = 0.001M$, Formamide = $0.1M$				$Temp = 35^\circ$
H_2SO_4	0.01	0.04	0.07	0.1	
$k' \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	5.00	4.60	4.11	3.60	
$k'' \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	1.21	1.09	0.85	0.71	
$k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	3.79	3.51	3.26	2.89	
	$= k' - k''$.				

It is seen that the specific rate slightly decreases with an increase in sulphuric acid concentration, the decrease being over 20% for ten-fold increase in sulphuric acid concentration. It may be pointed out that this decrease is much less than the decrease obtained due to an equivalent increase in ionic strength. This suggests that actually sulphuric acid (H^+) catalyses the reaction.

Effect of temperature

Table 4 gives the value of various energy parameters for this reaction.

ΔH^\ddagger as calculated by a plot of $\log \frac{k_r/kT}{h}$ vs $1/T$

comes out to be $15.56 \text{ KCals mole}^{-1}$ and this value of ΔH^\ddagger has been used to calculate ΔS^\ddagger reported above.

TABLE 4

Formamide = 0.1M, H₂SO₄ = 0.01M, AgNO₃ = 0.001M, K₂S₂O₈ = 0.01M

Temp. in °A	k × 10 ⁴ min ⁻¹	Temp. coefficient	Energy of activation (E) in KCals mole ⁻¹	Frequency factor sec. ⁻¹ A × 10 ⁻⁶	Free energy (ΔG [‡]) KCals mole ⁻¹	Entropy of activation (ΔS [‡]) e.u.
303	2.38			12.24	23.84	-28.13
308	3.79	2.31	15.86	12.91	23.94	-28.05
313	5.51	2.35	16.01	12.41	24.13	-28.17
318	8.64			12.82	24.24	-28.14
Mean		2.33	15.94 (16.02) Graphically	12.60	24.04	-28.12

The energy of activation for this reaction is found to be similar to that for the oxidation of dimethyl formamide¹. Furthermore the entropy of activation in the two cases is also negative and of similar order of magnitude. These facts suggest that the mechanism for the two reactions may be similar.

Since the reaction exhibits specific inhibitory effect, similar to that in S₂O₈²⁻-dimethyl formamide reaction, the effect of ionic strength has not been investigated in detail, although it has been observed that the salt effect is negative.

Effect of allyl acetate

The effect of a trace of allyl acetate (1 × 10⁻⁴M) on the rate of formamide reaction and of self-decomposition of peroxydisulphate ion is represented graphically in Fig. 3. It is clear that the inhibitory

Fig. 3. Effect of allyl acetate
K₂S₂O₈ = 0.01M, AgNO₃ = 0.001M,
H₂SO₄ = 0.01M, Temp. = 35°.
I● : in the absence of HCONH₂ and allyl acetate
II○ : in the absence of HCONH₂, and 1 × 10⁻⁴M allyl acetate
I× : HCONH₂ = 0.1M, no allyl acetate.
II◐ : HCONH₂ = 0.1M, allyl acetate = 1 × 10⁻⁴M.

effect on the two reactions is of similar order of magnitude, suggesting thereby that the radical (S) involved in self-decomposition and in formamide oxidation may be the same.

Mole ratio and analysis of products

The mole ratio for the reaction was determined after taking into account the self-decomposition of potassium peroxydisulphate in presence of the catalyst. This comes out to be 1 mole of potassium peroxydisulphate to 1 mole of formamide. The presence of formic acid during the course of reaction was detected by conventional tests, but at the end of reaction no formic acid remains; it decomposing into carbon dioxide and water. The presence of ammonia (NH₄⁺) during the entire course of reaction was detected by Feigl test⁴ showing thereby that ammonium ion in acidic medium does not get oxidised by S₂O₈²⁻ under the present condition.

In order to verify that formamide oxidation is in fact the oxidation of formic acid—a hydrolytic product and that NH₄⁺ ion does not undergo any appreciable oxidation, the kinetics of oxidation of formic acid alone and in the presence of NH₃ was carried out at different concentrations of the reactants, the data for which are summarized under Table 5.

TABLE 5

AgNO ₃ = 0.001M, H ₂ SO ₄ = 0.01M		Temp = 35°	
[K ₂ S ₂ O ₈] = 0.01M		[HCOOH] = 0.01M	
HCOOHM	K × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ M	K × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
0.01	9.42	0.005	13.64
0.02	12.97	0.0075	11.22
0.03	14.24	0.01	9.42
0.04	21.95	0.015	8.15
0.05	29.61	0.02	7.80

(HCOOH + NH₃)
each concentration 0.01M
9.26

From the above results it is seen that the rate for formic acid oxidation is of similar order of magnitude as that for formamide oxidation when the effect of

concentration is taken into account. Further the addition of ammonia does not affect the rate of oxidation. Besides this formic acid and formamide oxidation reactions are similar in this respect that variation of $K_2S_2O_8$ concentration affects the first order rate constant in a similar manner.

Discussion

The first order behaviour of the reaction in peroxydisulphate, zero order in formamide, linear relationship between specific rate and silver ion concentration, negative salt effect, decrease of specific rate with an increase in potassium peroxydisulphate concentration and increase of specific rate with an increase of formamide concentration and inhibition by traces of allyl acetate all go to show that this reaction is very much similar to the silver ion catalysed oxidation of dimethylformamide and is similar to the silver ion catalysed oxidation of alcohols by peroxydisulphate ion, studied by Khulbe and Srivastava and others. These similarities in kinetic behaviour and the observation that NH_4^+ has been found present throughout the course of the reaction, suggest to us that the reaction follows the mechanism :

It is worthwhile to point out that the first two steps have been proposed by Bawn and Margerison⁵ and by Srivastava and coworkers in other silver ion catalysed oxidation reactions of different substrates by peroxydisulphate ion⁶⁻⁹ also.

In view of the close similarity in kinetic behaviour for the oxidation of dimethyl formamide and formamide and other amides, it is assumed that the first two stages are the same in each case, followed by the oxidation of formic acid alone by the process (4) to (7) in case of dimethyl formamide and formamide. Thus the oxidation of amides really involves the oxidation of the hydrolytic product of its decomposition. On application of steady state treatment to the radicals Ag^{2+} , $SO_4^{\cdot -}$, $\cdot OH$, $HCOO\cdot$, the rate of consumption of peroxydisulphate ion works out to be,

$$-d \frac{[S_2O_8^{2-}]}{dt} = \left\{ k_1[Ag^+] + \left(\frac{k_1 k_2 k_6}{k_7} [Ag^+] \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\} [S_2O_8^{2-}] \quad \dots (iv)$$

The above expression clearly shows the first order behaviour in $S_2O_8^{2-}$ and independence of the rate of formamide concentration. However, the above expression does not clearly show the first order dependence of rate on Ag^+ concentration but at the same time it can safely be argued that the rate is related to a power of Ag^+ concentration not very much different from one. Thus, the above equation, though in conformity with the general kinetic behaviour, does not explain the observed dependence of specific rate on the initial concentration of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ and of $HCONH_2$. Evidently, the mechanism of Levitt and Malinowski¹⁰ for alcohol oxidation given to account for the dependence of specific rate on the concentration of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ and the organic substrate does not seem to be correct, which has also been questioned by Wiberg¹¹ on the basis of his tracer studies.

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